

Act Together To End COVID-19": Interactional Metadiscourse in The WHO's Speeches During The COVID-19 Pandemic

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ABSTRACT: Since the outbreak of the pandemic COVID-19, a huge amount of information has been released and shared by individuals, communities and specialized organizations. Language serves as a powerful tool on which information providers depend to convey their advice and instructions. In this study, the researchers examined the frequency of interactional metadiscourse markers in the WHO's director general's speeches regarding the COVID-19 pandemic and how those markers are used for communicative and persuasive effects. The corpus included 91 scripts with a different number of words making a total of 84,372 words. Hyland's (2005) model of metadiscourse was used to analyse the corpus. Data analysis revealed that interactional metadiscourse markers are heavily used by WHO director to deliver coherent speeches and to make his speeches persuasive. Moreover, the findings show that the speaker relied intensively on the use of self-mention marker and boosters to reflect the collaborative and assured attitude of the organization concerning the situation of the pandemic.

KEYWORDS: Covid-19; interactional markers; Metadiscourse; persuasion; WHO

1. INTRODUCTION

As a multi-disciplinary field, discourse analysis researches from numerous disciplines are rapidly growing. Many researches focused on the vital role of how addressees get the information that the addresser is trying to convey. Generally, speakers and writers endeavour to certify that the information they present is understood, accepted and acted upon. This can be achieved systematically by identifying the linguistics features of metadiscourse which provides a framework for understanding communication as a kind of social engagement.

Metadiscourse helps speakers/writers to involve addressees in their speeches/writing, engage and motivate them or perhaps persuade them. Hyland (2005) has referred to the relationship between metadiscourse and persuasion by describing metadiscourse as a rhetorical strategy used to persuade because it allows speakers and writers to plan their thoughts and interests into a text and to improve their propositions considering possible readers' perceptions (Hyland 2005:63). The persuasive function of metadiscourse in a text was sufficiently discussed and proven (see Hyland 1998, 2005; Mauranen 1993; Dafouz 2003). In such interpersonal dimension, the addresser takes in his consideration the addressees' reaction towards the discourse, how they will comprehend and respond to the information and how they are engaged in the interaction (Hyland 2005).

Metadiscourse has also been linked to the concept of the community since it is concerned with the fact that there is always communication in social contexts (Hyland 2005:132). This communication can be recognized by the discourse which, in turn, influences the community, as Swales (1988:212) highlighted "the discourse creates the community". In other words, community discourse offers a means of analysing communication. By understanding the notion of community influence on social interaction, it can be realized that discourse is socially located and emphasizes something of what writers/speakers bring to a text. And according to Hyland (2005:141) this is central to comprehend how metadiscourse works.

On the other hand, nowadays, linguistic features of communities are affected by the major health crisis of COVID-19 which has threatened the world population in many ways. The event of COVID-19 has led to an immense flow of communication between health organizations and the population. Many studies have referred to the role of media and its ability to spread information that can develop interactions between health organizations and the population (Chapman et al. 2014; Thackeray et

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al. 2008; Moorhead et al. 2013; Neiger et al. 2013). One of the official media sources of information is the World Health Organization (WHO) which adopted intervention as a policy to address the population and prepare them to face the pandemic.

However, a large amount of specialized discourse concerning COVID-19 has been constructed from the first moment of the virus existence. Researchers have taken this issue and the role of social media as an object of study. One of the studies is that conducted by Zhao (2020) who explored the quotidian expressions of nationalism that were posted by Chinese netizens on the Question and answer platform "Zhihu" during the period of the coronavirus. Another study was carried out by Tan et al. (2020). The researchers provided a valuable source of data and methods for discourse analysis within the recent situation of the pandemic. The article (Tan et al. 2020) presented some studies that dealt with various linguistic perspectives, such as analysing keywords related to public health in the Malaysian Hansard corpus. This includes transcripts concerning the Malaysian politicians and leaders' attitudes towards public health issues from 1998 to this date. Such studies offer insights into how public health issues are addressed from linguistic perspectives.

Similar studies have been proposed to examine COVID-19 texts. For example, inspecting the content of the context of Covid-19 posted on the social media platform China's Weibo and Baidu (Carvajal-Miranda et al. 2020); investigated the use of euphemism and dysphemism in the Jordanian society for dealing with COVID-19 (Olimat 2020); and exploring the way the news of COVID-19 is used for political and ideological purposes in two newspapers: The New York Times from the United States of America and Global Times from China (Abbas 2020).

Despite this wide range of discourses that have been under study, pandemic discourses proposed by health institutions and organizations have not been given enough attention in applied linguistic studies. Meanwhile, the forms of knowledge and instructions produced by health institutions or organizations are constituted through social interaction. As Heller (1995:374) stated, "the forms of knowledge which are privileged as expert knowledge in institutions, and taken to be inherently better for the accomplishment of institutional goals, are linked to the knowledge which is the cultural product of dominant group". Speech by health organizations is one of the examples of direct communication which consists of intent and the goal that the institution wants to convey to the public.

As the United Nations is an agency that is specialized in health, the WHO is the international body responsible for public health. WHO was established in 1948 and was involved in many aspects of health policy and planning. The mandate of the world health organization is "the attainment by all people of the highest possible level of health" (Lee, 2008). The serious challenge of fulfilling this purpose has required high-level technical skills. In 2020, the organization declared the outbreak of the covid-19 coronavirus a pandemic and coordinated international efforts to fight the virus by starting to issue guidelines on preventing the virus from being spread and treating the diseases. In addition, the organization has offered weekly media briefings addressing the population of the whole world to provide information about the status of the virus and to direct people during the period of the pandemic. Such a vital role of the organization is deserved to be focused on and the way in which the organization achieved its purposes needs to be explored.

To the best of the researchers' knowledge, no study so far has been conducted to investigate the function of the communicative devices of interactional metadiscourse and their linguistic realization in the discourse of health organizations. As long as such investigation would offer a descriptive picture on the extent to which the linguistics features of metadiscourse are employed to serve the purposes of public health discourse. Therefore, this paper raises the question of what communicative linguistic features of interactional metadiscourse in WHO's speeches are used to persuade the population to fight the virus and defeat or treat the disease. To this end, the speeches of the director-general of the World Health Organization (WHO) have been scrutinized metadiscoursally. Such exploration can provide insights into how metadiscourse devices are performed in the WHO's discourse. The findings from the study will put into perspective the importance of the linguistic features of metadiscourse in conveying official announcements and communications that aim at affecting public acceptance and compliance to emergency policy interventions, especially necessitated by crises such as the pandemic.

A. The aims of the study

This study aims to analyse the interactional metadiscourse markers in the public health discourse proposed by the WHO's director-general at the media briefing on the COVID-19 pandemic. It is hoped that such investigation will provide a descriptive picture of the way in which interactional resources are used in the health organization discourse, as well as, it will draw an idea about the organization tendencies and community preferences in their communicative language. By determining the interactional features of metadiscourse that characterize the public health discourse, we will be able to delineate the genre of health more precisely (Hyland 2005: 201).

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Concisely, this study seeks to address the following research questions:

1. What interactional devices of metadiscourse are used in the public health discourse of WHO to achieve its communicative and persuasive purposes?
2. How do interactional metadiscourse markers perform in the contexts of the public health discourse?

2. METHOD

A. Theoretical framework

Metadiscourse has always been considered as a fuzzy term. Scholars have offered a number of definitions of metadiscourse. Williams (1981) defined metadiscourse as "whatever does not refer to the subject matter being addressed". Similarly, Vande Kopple (1985) sees metadiscourse as "the linguistic material which does not add propositional information but which signals the presence of an author". Both of them have seen the concept of metadiscourse as a separate and secondary component of a discourse. However, Hyland (2005) argued that the meaning of a text depends on all the components of a text the propositional and metadiscoursal ones, as he (2005) stated "the meaning of a text depends on the integration of its component elements, both propositional and metadiscoursal, and these do not work independently of each other".

Hyland (2005) provided a clear and precise definition of metadiscourse according to which metadiscourse "is the cover term for the self-reflective expressions used to negotiate interactional meanings in a text, assisting the writer (or speaker) to express a viewpoint and engage with readers as members of a particular community". Based on this definition, Hyland (2005) classified metadiscourse into two categories, namely: interactive markers "help to guide the reader through the text"; and interactional markers "involve the reader in the text". The former category is subcategorized into transitions, frame markers, endophoric markers, evidentials, and code glosses markers. While, interactional metadiscourse is subcategorized into hedges, boosters, attitude markers, engagement markers, and self-mention markers.

In addition, to recognize metadiscourse materials in a text, Hyland (2005: 38) mentioned three key principles of metadiscourse: (i) "metadiscourse is distinct from propositional aspects of discourse"; (ii) "it refers to aspects of the text that embody writer-reader interactions"; and (iii) "it refers only to relations which are internal to the discourse". In Hyland's (2005) model, metadiscourse is divided into two main categories: interactive markers (involve shaping a context to meet addressees' needs); and interactional marker (concerned with involving addressees in the discourse).

Hyland (2005) has also linked the use of the categories of metadiscourse to the three appeals of persuasion, namely: ethos, pathos, and logos. The use of metadiscourse has often been considered as the attempt of writers/speakers to persuade readers/listens through making credible (ethos), affective (pathos), and rational (logos) appeals. It has been revealed that by using interactive metadiscourse markers writer/speaker can link their arguments logically and hence they can achieve logos (i.e. using reason in persuasion). While by using interactional markers of metadiscourse which are "looking at the text from the reader's perspective, addressing their situation, empathizing with their values, and goals and directly inviting them to respond", writers/speakers can achieve affective appeals or pathos. Finally credible or ethos appeals can be achieved by the use of hedges and boosters metadiscourse markers (Ho, 2016:6).

As long as each category of metadiscourse is clearly defined and can be distinctively identified, the classification of metadiscourse in Hyland's (2005) model was worth to be used as a guideline for identification of metadiscourse in any study. The model (2005) has become more applicable and has been adopted in many studies in different fields and disciplines, such as (Hyland and Tse 2004; Dahl 2004; AlJazrawi and AlJazrawi 2019; Mahmood and Kasim's 2019). Thus, to answer the questions of this study Hyland (2005) interactional classification of metadiscourse has been adopted, as shown in Table 1 below:

Table 1. Interactional Markers from Hyland's (2005) Model of Metadiscourse

Category	Function	Examples
Interactional	Involve the reader in the text	Resources
Hedges	withhold commitment and open dialogue	might, perhaps, possible, about
Boosters	emphasize certainty or close dialogue	in fact, definitely, it is clear that
Attitude markers	express writer's attitude to proposition	unfortunately, I agree, surprisingly
Engagement markers	explicitly build relationships with reader	can see that, note, consider
Self-mentions	explicit reference to author(s)	I, we, my, our

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B. Methodology

The study is quantitative in nature and focuses on the frequencies of occurrences of interactional markers in the public health discourse of the world health organization (WHO). Moreover, the qualitative approach is also adopted to provide a description of the performance of interactional metadiscourse in public WHO' speeches regarding the COVID-19 pandemic.

The corpus used in this study includes 91 scripts of the WHO's director general's speeches, totalling 84,372 words. The researchers compiled the texts purposively by reviewing WHO's scripted speeches released on the official website of the organization (www.who.net). As this research aims to draw attention to the communicative language of the health organization when it addresses the international population during the crucial period of the pandemic, only the speeches whose titles have to do with the "WHO Director-General's opening remarks at the media briefing on COVID-19" were selected. These speeches occurred between 5 February and 9 October of 2020. Normally all the speeches are provided in the English language.

As it was mentioned earlier, Hyland's (2005) model of metadiscourse was utilized to investigate interactional metadiscourse in the WHO's speeches on the COVID 19 pandemic. The list of interactional metadiscourse items provided by Hyland (2005:220-224) were used to identify metadiscourse in the public health discourse of WHO's speeches quantitatively. Based on the assumed function of the interactional markers provided in Hyland's (2005) model, the interactional items of metadiscourse were coded in the corpus using a concordance software program of AntConc (Anthony 2013). The list of items of the five categories of interactional markers was applied separately to the concordance search. After applying the lists of items to the concordance program, the returns of the concordance searches were shifted to Excel files in order to code them for the second time manually and delete the coded items with propositional function and keep the ones with metadiscoursal meanings. This distinction of the interactional metadiscourse was done based on the three key principles of metadiscourse proposed by Hyland (2005:38).

The qualitative approach focused on the content analysis to understand the discourse functions that interactional markers perform in the public health discourse to address the international population. A number of the identified items from each category were observed in the context to see how the function of the linguistic feature is relevant to the social purpose of the text.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The corpus of this study, as was mentioned earlier, consists of 91 scripts of the WHO's director general's speeches forming a total of 84,372 words. Data analysis revealed that the total number of interactional metadiscourse markers that appeared in the corpus is 5,678 as indicated in Table 2 below:

Table 2. Number and percentage of interactional metadiscourse markers in the corpus

Interactional Markers	
Number	Percentage
5,678	6.73%

The above table shows that the percentage of interactional markers in the corpus is 6.73% which indicates that 6 instances in every 100 words are used with a metadiscursive function and 67 instances in every 1000 words are used metadiscoursally.

As for the number and percentage of each of the five categories of interactional markers, it was found out that the most frequently used interactional marker is self-mention followed by boosters, engagement markers, attitude markers and finally comes hedges as shown in Table 3 below:

Table 3. Number and percentage of the five categories of interactional markers in the selected WHO's speeches

Interactional Markers	Number	Percentage
Self-mention	1,444	25.43%
Boosters	1,439	25.34%
Engagement Markers	1,086	19.13%
Attitude Markers	944	16.63%
Hedges	765	13.47%
Total	5,678	100%

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As is clear from the table, self-mention occurred 1,444 times in the data forming 25.43% of the total number of interactional markers in the data. This category of interactional markers is realized mainly through the use of exclusive 'we' which refers to I and one or others but not you (Gordon and Luke 2015). Exclusive we being used 1017 times followed by 'I' being used 328 times, then by 'my' being used 74 times and finally comes 'me' which appeared 25 times (see Figure 1). The intensive use of exclusive "we" may indicate the trying of the speaker to say that they (WHO's director and the members of WHO) collaboratively are handled the situation adeptly.

Figure 1 The distribution of self-mention marker in the selected WHO's speeches

Whereas, the speaker establishes a certain degree of distance (whether close or far) with the listeners and expresses his perspective through the use of "I". However, writers and speakers use this category of interactional markers to indicate their presence in their written/spoken discourse by the use of first-person pronouns and possessive adjectives for the purpose of expressing their point of view regarding their arguments, community and readers (Hyland 2005). Thus, through the use of this marker, speakers will be able to create persuasive speech by stimulating an ethos. In this respect, the speaker's credibility is the tool for achieving persuasion and listeners are being convinced by the speaker's judgment and goodwill which they trust.

The following are examples from the data:

1. "We also welcome the announcement by one vaccine developer, Moderna, that it will not enforce its patent rights over its COVID-19 vaccine during the pandemic." (9 October 2020)
2. "I hope you will be inspired by the many examples of successful programs, on adolescent mental health, suicide prevention, dementia and many more, that are being implemented by WHO, in collaboration with our partners." (9 October 2020)
3. "Over the weekend **my** friend, Boris Johnson, the Prime Minister of the United Kingdom, announced new funding for both WHO and COVAX, which is the vaccines arm of the ACT-Accelerator." (28 September 2020)
4. "Let **me** begin with the latest numbers." (5 February 2020)

Booster's marker is the second interactional metadiscourse category in terms of frequency of occurrence as shown in Table 3 above. This marker appeared 1,439 times in the data forming 25.34% of the total number of interactional markers. Writers and speakers use boosters to indicate that they are certain about what they say. Through the use of boosters and hedges, writers and speakers show that they are committed to their texts and speeches and that they respect their readers and listeners. 'Just', 'still', 'only', 'already', 'as I said', 'know', 'need', 'will', 'all' and 'the best' are among the most frequently used booster markers in the data. However, WHO's director prefers to achieve persuasion by means of assured declarations and being assertive rather than being indirect. In this sense, the credibility appeal (ethos) is the means of achieving persuasion.

The following are examples from the data:

5. "This isn't **just** the right thing to do, it's the smart thing to do." (21 September 2020)
6. "We **know for certain** that there will be future novel viruses and another so called disease X." (18 September 2020)
7. "In time, as production increases, we want **all** people everywhere to have access to vaccines." (4 September 2020)
9. "Once we have an effective vaccine, we **must** also use it effectively, and **the best** way to do that is by making sure it's available to all countries equitably through the COVAX Facility." (9 October 2020)

The engagement marker occupies the third position in terms of frequency of occurrence in the data. This category is used 1,086 times forming 19.13% of all of the interactional markers of metadiscourse. Engaging the readers and listeners in the writer's text or speaker's speech is the purpose behind using those markers. WHO' director achieves this by explicitly talking to their listeners through the use of pronouns like 'our', 'you', inclusive 'we', directives like 'consider', 'remember' and

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questions. Pronouns occupied the first position among engagement markers in terms of frequency, specifically the pronoun 'our' followed by 'you', 'we', 'together' and 'us'.

The following are examples from the data:

10. "If we all physically distance, clean **our** hands regularly, wear masks, and keep informed, we can collectively break the chains of transmission." (24 August 2020)
11. "My message to these patients was: we hear **you** loud and clear, and we are committed speaker to working with countries to ensure **you** receive the services **you** need, and to advancing research to serve **you** better." (21 August 2020)
12. "**We** must all learn to control and manage this virus using the tools we have now, and to make the adjustments to our daily lives that are needed to keep ourselves and each other safe." (21 August 2020)
13. "We must seize this moment to come **together** in national unity and global solidarity to control COVID-19, address antimicrobial resistance and the climate crisis." (6 August 2020)
14. "All of **us** have a role to play in reducing our risk of exposure to COVID-19." (30 July 2020)

The fourth position is occupied by attitude markers which formed 16.63% of interactional metadiscourse markers being used 944 times in the data as the above table shows. This marker indicates the interest of writers and speakers in expressing surprise, obligation, importance, agreement regardless of whether this information is related, reliable, or even true. Thus, using this marker enables WHO's director to persuade their listeners by affecting their emotions through emotional appeal (pathos). The instances of attitude marker in the data are realized by the use of attitude verbs, such as 'make', 'help', 'learn', adverbs such as 'quickly', 'inappropriately', 'deeply', and adjectives such as 'essential', 'common', 'difficult'.

The following are examples from the data:

15. "Every day, we all **make** decisions that affect our health and the health of those around us, in many ways." (30 July 2020)
16. "We must all **learn** to control and manage this virus using the tools we have now, and to make the adjustments to our daily lives that are needed to keep ourselves and each other safe." (21 August 2020)
17. "WHO is **deeply** concerned about the impact of COVID-19 on the global response to HIV." (7 July 2020)
18. "We continue to urge countries to focus on four **essential** priorities." (25 September 2020)
19. "We can only confront this **common** threat with a **common** approach." (21 September 2020)

Hedges marker was the least among other interactional markers. It occupies the fifth position in terms of frequency of occurrence. This marker appeared 765 times in the data forming 13.47% of all of the interactional markers of metadiscourse. Expressions such as the modal auxiliaries (may/might, can/could, should, would) are used by writers and speakers to express opinions and not facts and to give the impression that a certain statement is related to what they believe rather than to particular knowledge. Apart from modals, epistemic verbs (expect, appear), adverbs (relatively, likely), nouns (possibility) and approximators (almost, at least) also appeared in the data. WHO's speeches were involved with this type of interactional metadiscourse to convey WHO's instructions, warnings, declarations and facts indirectly. Since, the use of hedges enables writers/speakers to influence their readers/listeners to persuade them of their opinions and points of view or their way of thinking or behavior. Consequently, writers/speakers are able to create persuasive texts/speeches (cf. Halmari and Vritanen 2005).

The following are examples from the data:

20. "These diseases disfigure, disable and **can** kill, and they strike hardest in places of poverty and in remote areas where access to quality health services is extremely limited." (17 June 2020)
21. "It **would** also lead to a prolonged pandemic as only a small number of countries **would** get most of the supply." (24 August 2020)
22. "Last week we reached an important milestone, in which WHO issued the first Emergency Use Listing for a quality antigen based rapid diagnostic test and we **expect** other rapid tests to follow." (28 September 2020)
23. "The recent meeting of the G20 countries expressed strong support for Africa, which must be expedited even though the numbers in Africa are still **relatively** small but accelerating." (10 April 2020)
24. "**Almost** 16 million cases have now been reported to WHO, and more than 640,000 deaths." (27 July 2020)

Unfortunately, there are no available studies (investigated the interactional linguistic devices in international organizations) against which the findings of the current study can be compared. However, comparing the results of this study with previous researches specifically which involved political public speaking discourse shows some similarities in terms of the preferred marker used, such as the investigation of metadiscourse in speeches of minister for foreign affairs of Indonesia

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(Angraini and Effrianti 2020); in Michelle Obama's speech (Sari 2014); in the speeches of Barack Obama in his campaign 2012 (Sukma's, 2017); and in the speeches of the US presidents Obama and Trump (Mirzaeian's, 2020).

When comparing the results of the present study with previous researches, one can find that there are points of similarity and difference. The study of Angraini and Effrianti (2020) investigated interactional markers of metadiscourse in 10 speeches of the Indonesian Minister Foreign of Affairs. To analyze the data, the two researchers used Hyland's (2005) model of metadiscourse markers. The analysis revealed that all the interactional markers of metadiscourse appeared in the analyzed speeches of the minister, however, with different numbers and percentages. Self-mention is the marker that occupies the first position in terms of occurrence, followed by engagement markers, attitude markers, boosters and hedges. Thus, in both the current study and in Angraini and Effrianti study self-mention is the most frequently used marker and hedges is the least frequently used marker. However, whereas in the current study boosters marker is the second most frequently used marker followed by engagement marker and then attitude marker, in Angraini and Effrianti study, the second most frequently used is engagement markers followed by attitude markers and then boosters.

Sari's (2014) study aimed at identifying the types of metadiscourse markers used in the speech of Michelle Obama and discussing their functions. To analyze the data, the researcher adopted Hyland's (2005) classification. Data analysis showed that both of the categories of metadiscourse markers appeared in the speech of Obama with interactional markers being used more frequently than interactive markers. When closely inspecting the types of interactional markers employed by Obama in her speech, the researcher found out that self-mention is the highest in terms of the number and percentage of occurrence followed by hedges, engagement markers, boosters and attitude markers. Thus, this study confirms the results of the current study and that of Angraini and Effrianti in that self-mention is employed by speakers more than the other markers. As for the rest of the interactional markers, this study showed a pattern that is in a way different from those in the current study and Angraini and Effrianti study with hedges occupying the second position followed by engagement markers, boosters and attitude markers.

Sukma's (2017) study focused on the persuasive function of metadiscourse markers in spoken discourse by analyzing the speeches of Barack Obama in his campaign 2012. The researcher followed Dafouz's (2008) model of metadiscourse to analyze the data. Results of the analysis indicated that attitude markers were used more heavily by Obama in his speeches followed by commentaries, hedges, attributors and certainty markers. The researcher concluded that by relying more on attitude markers and commentaries, Obama was trying to affect his audience emotionally and to use this as his strategy of persuasion. It is worth mentioning that the category self-mention is included within commentaries in Dafouz's (2008) model of metadiscourse and here it occupies the second position in terms of occurrence.

Mirzaeian's (2020) study aimed at comparing the use of metadiscourse markers by the US presidents Obama and Trump in their speeches about the Iran nuclear deal to identify any factors that may affect the choice of these markers. To analyze the data, Dafouz's (2008) model of interpersonal metadiscourse markers was used by the researcher. Analysis of the data revealed that both of the presidents used commentaries more than the other markers followed by attitude markers, hedges, certainty markers and attributors. The result of this study is similar to that of Sukma's (2017) which both used the same model of analysis in that the first two metadiscourse markers in terms of occurrence are attitude markers and commentaries although in reverse order, the last two categories are attributors and certainty markers and in the middle comes the marker hedges. The results of Mirzaeian's (2020) study support those of the current study in that self-mention which is included in commentaries occupies the first position in terms of occurrence.

Whereas, some spoken discourse researches, such as academic spoken discourse (Lee and Subtirelu 2014) religious spoken discourse (Malmstrom 2016; Mahmood and Kasim 2019) show different results in which engagement marker is the most utilized category by the speakers. Thus, what is important for us to recognize here, is that this variation may indicate the specific nature of the genre of public health organizations.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The current study aimed at investigating interactional metadiscourse markers in the WHO's speeches on the COVID-19 pandemic. Analysis of the data revealed that these markers are relied on heavily in public health discourse by public speakers in this field in order to achieve coherence and cohesion and consequently produce cohesive and coherent speeches. Also, those markers are being used to produce persuasive speeches as one of the ways to create persuasive discourse is through the use of metadiscourse markers.

Public health speakers use interactional metadiscourse markers to show their commitment to their texts and to express their opinions and attitudes. In addition, they use such markers in order to engage their listeners in their speeches. The main reason

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behind this is to create persuasive speeches, and thus to persuade their listeners and convince them of their opinions and attitudes by means of the credibility appeal (ethos) and the affective appeal (pathos).

The results of the current study describe the use of the linguistic features of metadiscourse in the genre of public health organization which may profit those interested in rhetorical analysis of the public health discourses to replicate the success or avoid the failure of their discourse.

REFERENCES

- 1) Abbas, Ali Haif. (2020). politicizing the pandemic: A schemata analysis of covid-19 news in two selected newspapers. *International Journal for the Semiotics of Law-Revue internationale de Sémiotique juridique*: 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11196-020-09745-2>
- 2) AlJazrawi, Dunya A., and Zeena A. AlJazrawi. (2019). the use of Metadiscourse: An analysis of interactive and interactional markers in English short stories as a type of literary genre. *International Journal of Applied Linguistics & English Literature*, 8(3): 66-77.
- 3) Anthony, L. (2013). 'AntConc (Version 3.2.4m),' Tokyo, Japan: Waseda University, available at www.antlab.sci.waseda.ac.jp/. Accessed 10 September 2013.
- 4) Angraini, Ria, and Mirna Dwi Effrianti. (2020). Interpersonal Metadiscourse Markers in Speeches of Minister for Foreign Affairs of Indonesia. *Literary Criticism Journal*, 6(1)
- 5) Brown, Theodore M., Marcos Cueto, and Elizabeth Fee. (2006). the world health organization and the transition from "international" to "global" public health. *American Journal of Public Health*, 96(1): 62–72. <https://doi.org/10.2105/AJPH.2004.050831>.
- 6) Carvajal-Miranda, Christian, Luis Mañas-Viniegra, and Li Liang. (2020). online discourse in the context of COVID-19, the first health crisis in China after the advent of mobile social media: A content analysis of China's Weibo and Baidu. *Social Sciences*, 9(10): 167.
- 7) Chapman, Benjamin, Benjamin Raymond, and Douglas Powell. (2014). Potential of social media as a tool to combat foodborne illness. *Perspective Public Health*, 134: 225–30.
- 8) Dafouz-Milne, Emma. (2008). the pragmatic role of textual and interpersonal metadiscourse markers in the construction and attainment of persuasion: A cross-linguistic study of newspaper discourse. *Journal of pragmatics*, 40(1), 95-113.
- 9) Dahl, Trine. (2004). Textual metadiscourse in research articles: A marker of national culture or of academic discipline? *Journal of Pragmatics*, 36(10): 1807–1825.
- 10) Gordon, Cynthia, and Melissa Luke. (2016). "We Are in the Room to Serve Our Clients" We and professional identity socialization in E-Mail supervision of counselors-in-training. *Journal of Language and Social Psychology*, 35(1), 56-75.
- 11) Halmari, Helena, and Tuija Virtanen, eds. (2005). *Persuasion across Genres: A Linguistic Approach*. Amsterdam/Philadelphia: John Benjamins Publishing Company.
- 12) Heller, Monica. (1995). Language choice, social institutions, and symbolic domination. *Language in Society*, 24, 373-405.
- 13) Ho, Victor. (2016). Discourse of persuasion: a preliminary study of the use of metadiscourse in policy documents. *Text & Talk*, 36(1), 1-21.
- 14) Hughes, Christopher R. (2005). Interpreting nationalist texts: A post-structuralist approach. *Journal of Contemporary China*, 14(43): 247–267.
- 15) Hyland, Ken. (1998). Persuasion and context: The pragmatics of academic metadiscourse. *Journal of Pragmatics*, 30(4): 437–455.
- 16) Hyland, Ken. (2005). *Metadiscourse: Exploring Interaction in Writing*. London: Continuum.
- 17) Hyland, Ken, and Polly Tse. (2004). Metadiscourse in academic writing: A reappraisal. *Applied Linguistics*, 25(2), 156–177.
- 18) Lee, Joseph J., and Nicholas C. Subtirelu. (2015). Metadiscourse in the classroom: A comparative analysis of EAP lessons and university lectures. *English for Specific Purposes*. 37(1), 52–62.
- 19) Lee, Kelley. (2008). *the World Health Organization (WHO) (1st ed.)*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203029732>
- 20) Magnusson, Roger S. (2007). Non-communicable diseases and global health governance: Enhancing global processes to improve health development. *Globalization and Health*, 3(1), 2. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1744-8603-3-2>.
- 21) Mahmood, Israa Ismaeel, and Zalina Mohd Kasim. (2019). Interpersonal metadiscursive features in contemporary Islamic Friday sermon. *3L: The Southeast Asian Journal of English Language Studies*, 25(1): 85 – 99.

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- 22) Malmström, Hans. (2016). engaging the congregation: The place of metadiscourse in contemporary preaching. *Applied Linguistics*, 37(4): 561–582.
- 23) Mauranen, Anna. (1993). *Cultural Differences in Academic Rhetoric: A Textlinguistic Study*. Frankfurt: Peter Lang.
- 24) Mirzaeian, Elnaz. (2020). An Intra-cultural Analysis of Interpersonal Metadiscourse Markers Used in Obama and Trump’s Speeches on the Iran Nuclear Deal. *Corpus Pragmatics*, 1-15.
- 25) Milne, Emma Dafouz. (2003). Metadiscourse revisited: A contrastive study of persuasive writing in professional discourse. *Estudios Ingleses de La Universidad Complutense*, 11(1): 29–57.
- 26) Moorhead, S. Anne, Diane E. Hazlett, Laura Harrison, Jennifer K. Carroll, Anthea Irwin, and Ciska Hoving. (2013). A new dimension of health care: systematic review of the uses, benefits, and limitations of social media for health communication. *Journal of medical Internet research*, 15(4), e85.
- 27) Neiger, Brad L., Rosemary Thackeray, Scott H. Burton, Callie R. Thackeray, and Jennifer H. Reese. (2013). Use of twitter among local health departments: an analysis of information sharing, engagement, and action. *Journal of medical Internet research* 15(8), e177.
- 28) Olimat, Sameer Naser. (2020). COVID-19 pandemic: Euphemism and dysphemism in Jordanian Arabic. *GEMA Online Journal of Language Studies*, 20(3).
- 29) Peabody, John W. (1995). An organizational analysis of the World Health Organization: narrowing the gap between promise and performance. *Social science & medicine*, 40(6), 731-742.
- 30) Ruger, Jennifer Prah, and Derek Yach. (2009). the global role of the world health organization. *Global Health Governance. The Scholarly Journal for the New Health Security Paradigm*, 2(2), 1–11.
- 31) Sari, Aryati Meiga. (2014). *Interpersonal Metadiscourse Markers Used in Michelle Obama’s Speech*. Semarang: English Study Program, Faculty of Humanities, Dian Nuswantoro University.
- 32) Sukma, Bayu Permana. (2017). Interpersonal metadiscourse markers as persuasive strategies in Barack Obama’s 2012 campaign speeches. *Kompleks Indonesia Peace and Security Center*, 29(2), 283–292.
- 33) Swales, John. (1988). Discourse communities, genres and English as an international language. *World Englishes*, 7(2), 211-220.
- 34) Tan, Kim Hua, Peter Woods, Hazita Azman, Imran Ho Abdullah, Ruzy Suliza Hashim, Hajar Abdul Rahim, Mohd Muzhafar Idrus, Nur Ehsan Mohd Said, Robert Lew, and Iztok Kosem (2020). COVID-19 insights and linguistic methods. *3L: Language, Linguistics, Literature*, 26(2).
- 35) Thackeray, Rosemary, Brad L. Neiger, Carl L. Hanson, and James F. McKenzie. (2008). enhancing promotional strategies within social marketing programs: use of web 2.0 social media. *Health Promot Pract*, 9:338–43.
- 36) Vande Kopple, William, (1985). Some exploratory discourse on metadiscourse. *College Composition and Communication* 36: 82-93.
- 37) Williams, Joseph. M. (1981). *Style: Ten Lessons in Clarity and Grace*. Glen-view: Ill.:Scott, Foresman & Company.
- 38) Zhao, Xiaoyu. (2020). A discourse analysis of quotidian expressions of nationalism during the COVID-19 pandemic in Chinese cyberspaces. *Journal of Chinese political sciences*. 1-17.